

Reference List for: Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2022). Kategoriendenken: Implicit Bias im akademischen Kontext. Forschung & Lehre, 8, 132–133.

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Date: June 13, 2025

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References

1. Röhner, J., & Lai, C. K. (2021). A diffusion model approach for understanding the impact of 17 interventions on the race Implicit Association Test. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 47(9), 1374-1389.
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